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Parental Involvement in Relation to the Literacy and Numeracy Skills of Teenagers

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Abstract

The study examined how much parents support their teenagers in developing numeracy and literacy skills. The researchers used a mixed-methods approach through convenience sampling for the one hundred seniors in high school who took a 48-item literacy and numeracy test and filled out a survey about how involved their parents were. The researchers used a validated questionnaire and utilized the weighted mean, percentage, mean, Spearman Rank Order Correlation, Kruskal-Wallis Test, and Mann-Whitney U Test as the statistical tools. Focus group discussions (FGD) and key informant interviews (KII) also happened. Results say that family participation in terms of emotional support, money, and contact between parents and teachers is "high." However, teenagers could have done better on a 48-question test of reading, writing, and math skills. The data showed no significant relationship between emotional support, financial support, and contact between parents and teachers and how well teenagers did on reading and math tests. Also, parents' involvement stays the same when put into groups based on their profiles. Even with high parental involvement, teenagers from challenging households are more likely to drop out due to financial issues. Parents also need help paying for their children's transportation, income, and projects due to job losses and increasing commodity prices. Low-income teenagers have to choose school or work to eat. To keep their teenagers in school, unemployed mothers had to relocate for work. Meanwhile, parents recommend banning smartphones during class hours to prevent gadget dependence and boost focus.

Keywords: *Parental Involvement, Financial Support, Teenagers, Emotional Support, Parent-teacher Communication, Test Performance, Literacy & Numeracy Skills*

INTRODUCTION

After a few years of using different ways to learn in the Philippines, the Department of Education (DepEd), with help from the World Health Organization (WHO) and other groups, has brought back learning in person. Students were used to either modular online or printed learning, which meant getting textbooks, handouts, study notes, and other study tools in paper or digital form, as well as self-study modules (SLMs) in recent years. Most people now know that parents must work and attend school to care for their teenagers (Derrick et al., 2022). Cariaga's study from 2022 confirms Dayagbil et al.'s study from 2021 that teaching and parental involvement positively affect children's academic success. Parents should involve themselves in their teens' intellectual growth, according to Lawrence and Nkoane (2020). Beckman et al. (2019) observed that when students return to school, they still need help with basic skills like reading, writing, and math. Researchers may have thought that parents had a hard time helping their teenagers learn to be flexible because of what they did for a living, where they went to school, and how many teenagers they had (Boonk et al., 2018; Mishra et al., 2020). However, parents must monitor their teenagers' literacy and numeracy skills if they want success (UNICEF, 2020; Angrist et al., 2021). Literacy

skills refer to the ability to read and write (DepEd, 2020). The researcher's literacy exam results regarding communication, learning, and personal development operationally determined these skills. Meanwhile, numeracy skills refer to understanding and working with numbers (DepEd, 2020). Operationally, these abilities are helpful for problem-solving, decision-making, and everyday chores such as financial management.

Malabasbas et al. (2022) stressed the importance of getting a good education and offering extra help to needy teenagers. Since reading and math classes need grading (Bacomo et al., 2022), a good review can help teachers and students determine where they need more help ((Elifneh, 2021). Dee and Murphy (2021) noted that teenagers' math skills are below world and regional averages. Filipino teenagers could only do well on tests if they knew enough about language and math. If schools had put less emphasis on fixing problems and thinking critically, students in the Philippines might not have done better in literacy and numeracy. Lara and Saracosti (2019) said that more studies should determine how involved parents are and if schools need support. This study examined parental involvement, defined as emotional support, financial support, and parent-teacher communication. Hussain et al. (2020) suggested that teachers might learn how parents can help their teenagers do well in school

because the involvement of parents is a crucial factor in the academic achievement of teenagers. According to the World Health Organization (WHO, n.d.), teenagers are young learners in the growth and development between childhood and adulthood. Operationally, these are high school students between 15 and 19. The Philippines, a developing country with high poverty rates and an educational input deficit, exhibits a notable prevalence of school dropout rates among individuals experiencing poverty. Parents' age, sex, and occupation affected students' attendance (Gobena, 2018; Lara & Saracostti, 2019). Age refers to the parents' number of years of living, and sex refers to classifying reproductive organ functions (WHO, 2021). Occupation refers to a person's labor (Surbhi, 2015). Operationally, it refers to the work of parents or guardians. A study conducted in the Philippines has revealed a correlation between parents' academic engagement and their offspring's academic achievement during the initial years of schooling (Olivio, 2021).

Despite the absence of any extant local research, the potential influence of parental involvement in academic matters on adolescents' literacy and numeracy proficiency remains a pertinent query. Expressly, the extent to which parental academic involvement can impact their children's success in these domains warrants further investigation.

Statement of the Problem

The study aimed mainly to investigate the extent of parental involvement concerning teenagers' literacy and numeracy skills. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following research questions:

1. To what extent is parental involvement in terms of:
 - a. Emotional Support;
 - b. Financial Support;
 - c. Parent-Teacher Communication?
2. Is there a significant relationship between the profile of the parents and their extent of involvement in terms of:
 - a. age;
 - b. sex;
 - c. Parent's Occupation?
3. What is the extent of teenagers' literacy skills?
4. What is the extent of teenagers' numeracy skills?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of parental involvement and the teenagers' performance?
6. What other impacts do the teenagers experience regarding parental involvement in school to help improve their literacy and numeracy skills?

7. What development plan can be devised to foster solid parental support in school to improve teenagers' literacy and numeracy skills?

Statement of the Null Hypotheses

There is no significant relationship between the level of participation of parents and their teenagers' skills in literacy and numeracy.

There is no significant difference between the parents' profile and their level of participation.

METHODOLOGY

The researcher used a mixed-methods approach for the one hundred seniors in high school who took a 48-item literacy and numeracy test and filled out a survey about how involved their parents were. The researchers used a validated questionnaire and utilized the weighted mean, percentage, mean, Spearman Rank Order Correlation, Kruskal-Wallis Test, and Mann Whitney U Test as the statistical tools. Focus group discussions (FGD) and key informant interviews (KII) also happened. This study was done in one of the senior high schools in Negros Oriental in the school year 2022-2023. Aside from the convenience sampling of 100 students for quantitative data, the study added a qualitative discussion with a key informant to learn more about how parents helped their teenagers improve their reading and math skills. It was done to get a variety of experiences, points of view, and honest views about the study's factors (UCLA, 2020). Regarding students' skills, the 48-item test with primary English language and general math concepts determined how well students could read and do the math. The test followed the Department of Education's Table of Specifications (TOS) to ensure the items were valid, reliable, and spread out somewhat. The researchers used a questionnaire they created and reading and math tests for the teenagers. The study form consists of four parts: Part 1 collects general information about the parents' profile, such as age, gender, and the parent's job. Part 2 measures how much they think their parents help them emotionally, financially, and through contact with their teachers. Part 3 asks parents about their involvement and problems. Part 4 adds to the notes and suggestions about improving their reading and math skills. In this study, face validity was used to know how a thorough questionnaire looks in terms of how useful it is, how easy it is to read, how consistent the style and arrangement are, and how clear the language is (Olumatayo, 2012). Three experts in the field checked the instruments to see if they met the standards Good

and Scates (1972) set. Cronbach's alpha (0.798) showed that there was good internal stability. In the meantime, this study was tried again to see if the tool correctly caught the idea and if it got the same results. Concerning how the data was collected, the researcher asked the right people for permission to do the study. After getting permission, the researcher asked for permission from interested students and told them what the study was about, how much they would have to do, and their privacy rights. After spreading and collecting the questionnaire, the data were recorded, ordered, analyzed, and correctly translated using the Social Science Statistical Package (SPSS) program. Also, the collected data went through data processing and checking with the help of the experts' peers in the field to ensure the data was correct before interpretation. For the statistical treatment of data, appropriate statistical tools were used to answer the research questions. Percentage showed how a part is related to a whole. It was used to present the profile of the respondents. Weighted mean was used to identify the extent of the parent's participation as perceived by the students in terms of emotional support, financial support, and parent-teacher communication. It was interpreted using the following scale:

Table 1. Scaling and Verbal Description on the Extent of Parental Involvement (EoPI)

Scale	Verbal Description	Extent of Parental Involvement (EoPI)
6.15 – 7.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Very High (VH)
5.29 – 6.14	Agree (A)	High (H)
4.43 – 5.28	Somewhat Agree (SoA)	Somewhat High (SoH)
3.57 – 4.42	Neither Agree nor Disagree (NAD)	Moderate (M)
2.71 – 3.56	Somewhat Disagree (SoD)	Somewhat Low (SoL)
1.85 – 2.70	Disagree (D)	Low (L)
1.00 – 1.84	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Very Low (VL)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 shows the Extent of Parental Involvement in terms of Emotional Support. The result indicates that parental involvement is "high," as evident in the composite weighted mean of 5.70. The data also indicate that parents who (1) encouraged their children to attend school (wx = 6.02), (2) sought out ways to comfort children during difficult times (wx = 5.93), (3) continually reminded their children of their presence (wx = 5.92), and (4) offered comfort and listened to their children's problems (wx = 5.30) have high levels of parenting skills. These results imply that parents are trying their best by providing emotional support while

providing financial to send their teenagers to school. Their high involvement demonstrates a good outlook on educating their teenagers to achieve educational success. In addition, parents are also actively involved in their teenagers' education to support their academic achievement and give them greater self-assurance when faced with challenging tasks at home. Luaa (2021) confirmed that parents supported their adolescents. According to Nayak and Kunmari (2018), how parents deal with their teenagers could affect their teens' behaviors. Despite the challenges parents, children, and the school community face, determining parents' participation is crucial to student education (Nayak & Kumari, 2018). Family participation, compassion, freedom, and aid may help youngsters develop more socially and emotionally sophisticated, better regulate their emotions, and get along with others. Thus, parental emotional support is needed for instructional methods, educational programs, and school resources that help teenagers learn faster, keep up with their peers, meet learning standards, and succeed in school (Bacomo et al., 2022). Because parental participation enhances cognitive development, schools may implement programs to address dropout rates, low grades, and bad behavior (Novianti, 2020). Budhrani et al. (2021) said that parental academic encouragement affects a child's motivation and character, and Luaa (2021) demonstrated that parents support their children's education to help them build social intelligence (Nayak & Kunmari, 2018).

Table 2. Extent of Parental Involvement in terms of Emotional Support

Indicators	wx	VD	EoPI
1. My parents encouraged me to go to school.	6.02	A	H
2. My parents seek ways to comfort me in times of challenges at school.	5.93	A	H
3. My parents constantly remind me that they are always there for me.	5.92	A	H
4. I get comfort from my parents whenever I look tired because of school.	5.30	A	H
5. My parents listen to my problems and think of ways to solve them.	5.30	A	H
Composite	5.70	A	H

Table 3 presents the extent of parental involvement in terms of financial support. The combined weighted mean of 5.71 demonstrates that the parents offer "high" levels of financial support. In particular, the results show that the parents train their children to a "very high" level by helping them pay for school and getting them to school (wx = 6.18). It means

that parents who support their children's desire to learn do so with enthusiasm. It fits with the findings of Bacatan et al. (2022) that parents' level of interest significantly impacts their children's desire to learn and school growth by giving them the tools they need to know and pushing them to do well. The table also shows that the parents (a) look for ways to send their teenagers to school without them going hungry (wx = 6.04), (b) know about their teenagers' school projects so they can budget for them every month (wx = 5.60), and (c) do not complain about their teenagers' school allowance or daily fare and school expenses (wx = 5.15). Parents take part in these activities to a "high" degree. Parents need to help their teenagers learn, especially in this adjustment period as students resume in-person classes help (Elifneh, 2021). Tao et al. (2019) found that parents are involved in school when they are interested in their children's education. When teenagers learned to read when they were young, they knew more about paper, words, and the names and sounds of letters. Learning to read younger helped with math skills. How much money someone had, how active their family was, and who taught the program all played a role in whether or not they got to move (Dulay et al., 2018). Priyam and Nath (2021) suggest that family engagement, compassion, freedom, and assistance may help children become more socially and mentally mature, manage their emotions, and better get along with others. Though money from parents may enhance a teen's mental health and lessen anxiety, some may not. Schools may design parenting programs by showing how family support influences teenagers' mental health and academic achievement (Lindell et al., 2020). Youth with enough financial assistance, better family ties, and fewer negative family interactions attended school more often (Bartoszuk et al., 2019; Lindell et al., 2020).

Table 3. Extent of Parental Involvement in terms of Financial Support

Indicators	wx	VD	EoPI
1. My parents always provide me with my daily school allowance.	6.18	SA	VH
2. They always look for ways to send me to school without starving.	6.04	A	H
3. My parents include my daily allowance and possible class projects in their monthly budget.	5.60	A	H
4. My parents see that they know about my school projects, so they can budget for them.	5.60	A	H
5. My parents do not complain about my school allowance or daily fare and school expenses.	5.15	A	H
Composite	5.71	A	H

Table 4 presents the extent of parental involvement in communicating with teachers. The combined weighted mean of 6.03 shows that, according to the figures, parents' participation is "high." So, the data show that the parents are "very highly" involved in

talking to teachers about how their teenagers are doing in school (wx = 6.28), and they always go to school meetings, even if it means taking time off work (wx = 6.40). Even during the pandemic, the parents are in charge of getting the lessons, extra activities, and the results of the performance job for their children and sending them in. When the in-person classes resume, they support attending meetings. It fits with what Chen found in 2021 that parents interested in their teenagers' learning are perceived to be in charge of supporting their teenagers. There is a strong relationship between family participation and how well students do in school. Students do better in school if their parents communicate more with teachers (Ntibi et al., 2020; Hussain et al., 2020).

Table 4. Extent of Parental Involvement in terms of Communication with Teachers

Indicators	wx	VD	EoPI
1. My parents like to talk to my teacher about my school performance.	6.28	SA	VH
2. My parents always attend school meetings even if it means they have to take absences from their job.	6.40	SA	VH
3. My parents like to communicate with my teacher through texts and phone calls.	6.02	A	H
4. My parents feel motivated about my study when going to school during PTA meetings.	5.43	A	H
5. My parents are expressive in supporting whatever educational programs my school has.	6.02	A	H
Composite	6.03	A	H

Table 5 reveals the performance of teenagers in the literacy and numeracy skills test. The data indicated that the overall performance of the teenagers is below the passing score, which means that literacy (79.21%) and numeracy (76.38%) tests for teenagers fell below expectations, despite the high involvement of parents. It could be related to different types of learning problems. Because COVID-19 spread, many schools had to close, and much learning was lost worldwide (UNESCO, 2020). The closing of schools has hurt children's education and health in a big way and for a long time (UNICEF, 2020).

A child who misses a year of school because of the pandemic could lose up to three years of learning in the long run, according to UNESCO (2020) and Angrist et al. (2021). Bendanillo (2022) also noticed that helping parents read with their teenagers at home has changed over the last few decades. Instead of getting teenagers involved at school, the goal is to teach parents how to work with their teenagers at home (Derrick et al., 2022). About half of the world's students were still falling behind because they needed the correct literacy and numeracy skills (Dee & Murphy, 2021), and children lost more than the number of school days they missed during the pandemic (UNESCO, 2021).

Table 5. Performance of Teenagers in the Literacy and Numeracy Skills Test

Performance	Mean Score	Percent (%)
Literacy	19.01	79.21
Numeracy	18.33	76.38

Table 6 shows the data used to determine the relationship between how much parents help are involved and how well their teenagers perform in a literacy and numeracy skills exam. Using Spearman Rank Order Correlation to look at the three ways parents are involved in this study, the results show that none of the p-values are below the significance level (0.05). This finding will not prove that the null hypothesis is wrong. It means that there is no significant relationship between the parents' help with emotional support ($p = 0.192$), financial support (0.065), or contact with teachers ($p = 0.399$) and how well their teenagers did on the literacy and numeracy tests. This finding means the teenagers' literacy and numeracy scores cannot be explained by their parent's involvement in the areas listed. The table also shows that parents are very involved in their children's education, but teachers still have room to show more interest in the subject matter. Since these parents have no formal schooling in reading, they have a long way to go before teaching their children how to read correctly (Bendanillo, 2022). Grabe et al. (2020) say that most rural parents must have finished basic school before they can help their children learn at home. Why? Parents cannot ensure their teenagers get a good education, even during the most challenging school year (Mishra et al., 2020). Even if parents understand the lesson's main ideas, the United Nations (2020) says they need to gain the skills they need to teach these ideas to their children in the right way. Getting more parents involved in schools for these or several other reasons will not help teenagers do better (Derrick et al., 2022).

Table 6. Relationship between the Extent of Parental Involvement and the Teenagers' Literacy and Numeracy Skills Performance

Variables Correlated to Students' Literacy and Numeracy Performance	χ^2	p-value	Decision	Remark
Emotional Support	3.30	0.192	Failed to reject H_{01}	Not significant
Financial Support	5.48	0.065	Failed to reject H_{01}	Not significant
Communication with Teachers	1.84	0.399	Failed to reject H_{01}	Not significant

Table 7 shows how the amount of parental involvement changes when they are put into groups based on their profiles. Using the Kruskal-Wallis Test for age and sex and the Mann-Whitney U Test for employment, the results show that all p-values are higher than the significance level (0.05). This result will not be enough to prove that the null hypothesis is wrong. It means the parents' involvement stays the same when grouped based on the profile factors. It also means that the parent's involvement is the same no matter how old they are, what they do for a living, or what gender they are. According to studies by Ma et al. (2016) and Lui et al. (2020), students will do well in school no matter who their parents are as long as they care about their education. These results go against what Malabarbas et al. (2022) found about family involvement. The data showed that the parents' monthly income significantly impacts their children's learning. On the other hand, Yasmeen and Ejaz (2021) say that a family's monthly income indicates how involved the parents will be in learning despite the parent's profile on sex (Barni et al., 2022).

Table 7. Analysis Table on the Difference in the Extent of Parental Involvement when Grouped according to Profile

Profile	N	Mean Rank	Median	Comp. Value	p-value	Decision	Remark
Age							
35 yrs. old below	36	50.9	5.67	H = 0.28	0.869	Failed to reject H_{01}	Not significant
36-50 yrs. old	42	52.0	5.68				
51 up yrs. old	22	50.7	5.83				
Sex							
Male	72	54.4	5.80	U = 870.5	0.184	Failed to reject H_{01}	Not significant
Female	28	45.6	5.63				
Parent's Occupation							
Self-employed	19	59.0	6.01	H = 5.32	0.070	Failed to reject H_{01}	Not significant
Employed to Others	42	56.3	5.88				
Housewife	39	43.4	5.58				

Through Key Informant Interviews (KII), teenagers identified numerous experiences in which their parents supported their studies in school.

Dropping Out to Find Work

Key informants noticed that teenagers in unstable homes are likelier to quit school. During a focus group discussion (FGD), one of the students said that some of them dropped out of school to find work to help their families. When asked why they did not keep going to school, another student said that students whose parents lose their jobs tend to drop out because they do not have the resources to support themselves in school. Another student said, "Usually, it has to do with money, and because the parents live so far away, they cannot take good care of the teenagers." Because of this,

teenagers from low-income families often had to choose between going to school and getting food to eat by finding work because of budget constraints. However, informants noticed that some parents would not allow their teenagers to stop schooling. Some mothers who stayed at home were starting to find ways to support their teenagers through employment in a nearby municipality as cashiers, caretakers, and caregivers, going against their husbands' will to stay home and take off their house. Even some mothers who could not find work nearby would have to leave their province to find a job for their teenagers to continue studying.

Challenges in In-Person Classes

Under the new standard school structure, it took much work for Informant 1 to do in-person things. When they returned to face-to-face classes, it was hard for their parents to pay for their school needs because some had lost their jobs due to the pandemic. The face-to-face classes also made it hard for parents to figure out how to pay for their teenagers' daily transportation, allowance, and subjects. Informant 2 said some parents got angry when their teenagers had more questions while doing activities because the lessons were challenging and told them to ask their teachers. The questioning process got more challenging than before. Teachers could not answer students' questions quickly because some were teaching topics not in their areas of knowledge. Informants 3 and 4 said that teachers and parents should help teenagers adjust by encouraging them to listen and remember what teachers say. This way, teenagers will not have questions outside of school. Even though smartphone signals made it harder for people to talk to each other, source 4 said that teachers might give extra time to students who could not finish their work because they did not have tools. It would make it easier for students to ask questions about topics and activities that needed clarification.

Gadget Addiction Worries Parents

Informant 5 said money should be fine for parents who send their teenagers to face-to-face lessons. She worries about being too dependent on the excessive use of gadgets because she is a mother and an old student who returned to school. Her teenagers used devices daily, which was hard for her to watch because of her schedule. Informants 6 and 7 also noticed that their fellow students played cell phone games in their assigned spots during class, even though the teachers told them not to. They worry that being addicted to devices could make it hard to do well in school. They

think schools should have strict rules about using cell phones in class to prevent this.

CONCLUSION

Parents are involved in their teenagers' education, encouraging academic achievement and fostering self-confidence. The "high" levels of parental motivation in terms of emotional and financial support and communication with teachers encouraged students to pursue their schooling. Meanwhile, both results in literacy and numeracy tests for teenagers were low, despite the high involvement of parents. No correlation was found between parental involvement and the literacy and numeracy test scores of teenagers, thus indicating that parental involvement is not a factor in achieving educational success for teenagers during in-person classes after the pandemic. Sources show that teenagers from hard homes are likelier to drop out of school because of money problems, even if their parents are involved. Parents have needed help paying for their children's transportation, allowance, and school projects. Teenagers with low incomes had to choose between going to school and getting a job so they could eat. Mothers who could not find jobs in their area had to move so their teenagers could stay in school. Parents worry about teenagers becoming too dependent on technology and suggest schools ban smartphones to stop this from happening.

Recommendations

Division Superintendent. The Department of Basic Education may develop a two-year curriculum recovery plan to trim the curriculum in 2025. The articulated recovery teaching plans will set out a strategy to re-focus on teaching actual core content and improving teachers' understanding of competency levels concerning curriculum requirements, specifically, on the losses of acquiring basic literacy and numeracy skills.

Curriculum Developers and Planners. Management strategies can be crafted for schools to provide an avenue for parental support through concrete development plans.

District Supervisors. Present teaching and learning processes may be modified to suit the local needs of students, thus maximizing avenues for parents to be trained on how to provide support for their teenagers in terms of literacy and numeracy.

School principal. They may assign and designate reading teachers that will solely focus on the remediations to learners classified as low performers in literacy and numeracy. Findings can be used to craft safe, educational programs and more appropriate instructional materials to empower learners after the pandemic.

Teachers. They will be more aware of their students and the parents' experiences, thus encouraging teachers to have strategies or action plans to help parents support their teenagers in literacy and numeracy.

Parents. They will be capacitated on how they can be guided in their approach to upgrading their teenagers' literacy and numeracy skills.

Students. Parents will give them enough time and support while improving their literacy and numeracy skills.

Future researchers. The findings of this study can be a reasonable basis for future related studies and similar investigations.

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